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Depression amongst Aged in Context of Some Psycho-Social Factors

*Prof. (Dr.) Dinesh Kumar**

An attempt was made to examine the influence of some prominent psycho-social factors on depression amongst aged. The psychological factors were cognitive style, ego-strength and stress and social factors were social support, biological sex, SES and inhabitation. The purpose was to examine the influence of these factors on depression. It was hypothesized that : (1) Cognitive style, ego-strength and stress would have significant association with depression amongst aged people. (2) Social support, sex-difference, SES and Inhabitation all would have significant association with depression amongst aged people. Cognitive style, ego-strength, stress, social support and SES were measured using Witkin's EFT, Hasan's Ego-Strength Scale, SPSSI, Social Support Scale by Asthana and Verma and Bhardwaj SES Scale respectively. Depression was measured using Jamuar's MDI. The obtained data were analysed using chi-square. Both the hypotheses were retained. It was concluded that (1) Field independent group of aged people, high ego-strength group of aged people and moderate stress level group of aged people all are less likely to be the victim of depression. (2) High social support group, males aged group, high SES aged group and urban inhabitation aged group all are exposed to less likely to depression.

Introduction

The first component is depression which referred a feeling of severe and prolonged sadness, sometimes accompanied by total apathy, that occurs as a reaction to stress, possible influenced by chemical imbalances in the brain. According to Davison and Neale (1978) depression is an emotional state marked by great sadness and apprehension, feeling of with lessens and guilt, withdrawal from others, loss of sleep, appetite, sexual desire and either lethargy or agitation. Similarly Reber et al. (2009) defined depression as a mood state characterized by a sense of inadequacy, a feeling of dependency, a decrease in activity or reactivity, pessimism, sadness and related symptoms. Cognitive style refers to self evident modes of functioning which the individual shows in his perceptual and intellectual activities. There are several types of cognitive functioning among which field dependence and field independence are well known. A field dependence person is fund passive and less competent in analytical functioning having greater social orientation. On the other hand, a field independent person is found more active and competent in analytical functioning having less social orientation. Operationally, a field dependent person takes more time in perceiving an object as compared to his field independent counterpart. Field dependent persons rely on bodily sensation cues rather than causes in the field. The term 'ego-strength' has been defined as the tolerance capacity of the individual faced with the stressful situation. It means tolerance of anxiety and grasp of reality. People with strong ego have high tolerance of anxiety and firm grasp of reality. On the other hand people with weak ego are found to be confused, un-adaptive, rigged, stereotyped and unoriginal. Stress refers to an unpleasant state in which people perceived the demands of an event as taking or exceeding their ability to satisfy or alter those demands. The next component is social support which refers to our social network including people, on whom we can rely, people who let us know that they care about value

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and love us. It also refers to potentially useful coping resources providing by other people (Cobb 1976).

Some studies have been done in India and abroad showing the link of personality factors with depression. Williams (1990) found psychoticism, extraversion and neuroticism linked significantly with depression. Chaudhary et al. (1996) found extraversion and neuroticism dimensions of personality significantly linked with depression. The consequences of stress have also been examined in terms of psychosomatic problems (Kumar et al. 1977). These references indicated that the association of variables under reference with depression have not been examined in context of Patna, Bihar. Hence, the undertaking of the present study seems justified and warranted.

Objectives intends to

- (1) examine the association of cognitive style, ego-strength and stress with depression amongst aged people.
- (2) examine into the influence of social support, sex difference, SES and Inhabitation on the level of depression amongst the aged people.

Hypotheses

- (1) Cognitive style, ego-strength and stress would have significant association with depression amongst aged people.
- (2) Social support, sex-difference, SES and Inhabitation all would have significant association with depression amongst aged people.

Method of the Study

Design Employed

The study comprised of independent variables namely cognitive style, ego-strength, stress, social support, sex-difference, SES and inhabitation. Each independent variable is divided into two desired groups having distinct respondents. So, use of between comparable group design was preferred.

Sample Used

The sample comprised of 100 respondents [males (N = 50), females (N = 50) equally belonging to urban (N = 50) and rural (N = 50) inhabitation]. They were selected from among aged population of central and peripheral areas of Patna town using purposive sampling. Other than the present research condition of research they were matched so far as practicable.

Tools Used

- A PDS was used to seek the necessary information about the aged respondents.
- Witkin's EFT was used to measure cognitive style and group them into FI & FD groups.
- Hasan's Ego-Strength Scale was used to measure ego-strength of the respondents.
- SPSSI was used to measure level of stress of the aged respondents.
- Social Support Scale by Asthana Madhu and Verma Kiran Bala was used to measure social support of the respondents.
- Bhardwaj's SES Scale along with PDS was used to measure SES of the respondents.
- Jamuar's MDI was used to measure depression of the respondents.

Scale Administration for Data Collection

The respondents were administered scales along with PDS as per the convenience of the respondents and data were obtained. Thereafter, median cuts were used to divide them into to desired groups. For the purpose, 100 male aged and 100 female aged were administered the scales and finally 100 aged respondents were selected in such a way that

they must be equal in respect of each of the two divided desired groups in respect of each of independent variable (N = 50 each groups : males, females, urban, rural). Finally, the scores on MDI by them were compared in terms of dependent variable (depression) using chi-square. The results thus obtained are as follow:

Results and Interpretation

Table - 01

Chi-square showing the association of cognitive style, ego-strength and stress with depression of the aged respondents.

Variables	Groups	N	Depression		χ^2	df	P
			High	Low			
Cognitive Style	FI	44	67% (N=30)	33% (N=14)	14.73	1	<.01
	FD	56	40% (N=22)	60% (N=34)			
Ego-strength	High	48	31% (N=15)	69% (N=33)	13.35	1	<.01
	Low	52	65% (N=34)	35% (N=18)			
Stress	High	64	70% (N=45)	30% (N=19)	29.17	1	<.01
	Moderate	36	32% (N=12)	68% (N=24)			

The results displayed by table-01 clearly revealed the significant association of cognitive style with depression of the respondents. More than 67% (N=30) of FI group and only 40% (N=22) of FD group manifested acute depression. On the other hand only 33% (N=14) of FI group and more than 60% (N=30) of FD group manifested low depression. The chi-square was found significant ($\chi^2 = 14.73$; $df = 1$; $p < .01$).

Further, more than 79% (N=33) of high ego-strength group and only 35% (N=18) of poor ego-strength group manifested low depression. On the other hand only 31% (N=15) of high ego-strength group and more than 65% (N=34) of poor ego-strength group of respondents manifested acute depression. The chi-square was found significant ($\chi^2 = 13.35$; $df = 1$; $p < .01$).

Finally, more than 70% (N=45) and 32% (N=12) of respondents of high and moderate stress groups of respondents manifested high depression. Contrary to it, only 30% (N=19) and more than 68% (N=24) of high and moderate stress groups manifested low depression. The chi-square was found significant ($\chi^2 = 29.17$; $df = 1$; $p < .01$). Thus, hypothesis no. (1) is retained. The findings might be interpreted on the ground that respondents belonging to field independent group, high ego-strength group and moderate stress group are found having high level of confidence, full of enthusiasm leading to less likely to be the victim of depression.

Table - 02

Chi-square showing the association of social support, sex-difference, SES and Inhabitation with depression.

Variables	Groups	N	Depression		χ^2	df	P
			High	Low			
Social Support	High	43	29% (N=12)	71% (N=31)	27.66	1	<.01
	Low	57	66% (N=38)	34% (N=19)			
Sex-difference	Male	50	30% (N=15)	70% (N=35)	29.17	1	<.01
	Female	50	68% (N=34)	32% (N=16)			
SES	High	50	28% (N=12)	72% (N=30)	33.96	1	<.01
	Low	50	69% (N=40)	31% (N=18)			
Inhabitation	Urban	50	31% (N=15)	69% (N=35)	24.75	1	<.01
	Rural	50	66% (N=33)	34% (N=17)			

The results displayed by table-02 clearly revealed the significant association of social support, sex difference, SES and inhabitation with depression of the respondents. More than 71% (N=31) of high social support group and only 29% (N=12) of this group manifested low and high degree of depression respectively. Contrary to it, more than 66% (N=38) of low social support group and only 34% (N=19) of this group manifested high and low depression respectively. The chi-square was found significant ($\chi^2 = 27.66$; $df = 1$; $p < .01$).

Similarly, 70% (N=35) of males and only 30% (N=15) of this group manifested low and high depression. On the other hand, 68% (N=34) of female and only 32% (N=16) of this group manifested high and low depression. The chi-square was found significant ($\chi^2 = 29.17$; $df = 1$; $p < .01$).

Further, high SES 72% (N=30) group of respondents manifested low depression where as more than 69% (N=40) of low SES group manifested high depression. The chi-square was found significant ($\chi^2 = 33.96$; $df = 1$; $p < .01$).

Finally, urban respondents 69% (N=35) excelled in respect of having lower depression while rural people excelled in respect of having high depression 66% (N=33). The chi-square was found significant ($\chi^2 = 24.75$; $df = 1$; $p < .01$). Thus hypothesis no.(2) is retained. The findings might be interpreted on the ground that high social support group, male group, high SES group and urban inhabitation group all have higher level of confidence, high life satisfaction, sound mental and physical health leading to less likely to be the victim of depression.

Conclusions

- (1) Field independent group, high ego-strength group and moderate level of stress group of aged people all are less likely to be the victim of depression.
- (2) High social support group, male group, high SES group and urban inhabitation group of aged people all are less likely to be exposed to depression.

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